

Impact of OM Chanting and Alternate Nostril Breathing on Healthy Adults' Respiratory Endurance and Pulmonary Functioning

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Abstract:

Introduction: Pranayam is the most ancient basis of yoga practice. Regular practice of Pranayam and Om chanting can affect different body systems, especially the respiratory system. This research is designed to study the effectiveness of age-old practices like Alternate Nostril Breathing (ANB) and Om chanting on the respiratory system.

Aim: To evaluate the effectiveness of ANB and Om chanting on spirometric parameters and respiratory endurance.

Materials and Methods: An interventional study was conducted in the Department of Physiology at the Faculty of Medicine and Health Sciences, SGT University, Gurugram, Haryana, India. The study duration was eight weeks, and a total of 149 subjects, including both male and female participants aged between 18 and 25 years, were included in this study. Baseline recordings of anthropometric parameters, spirometric parameters like FEV₁, FEF_{25-75%}, and respiratory endurance parameters like BHTi, BHTe, and 40mmHg were recorded before the start of the study and again after eight weeks of intervention.

A comparison of spirometric parameters and respiratory endurance was done using the paired t-test.

Results: Comparison of spirometric parameters (FEV₁, FEF_{25-75%}) at baseline and after eight weeks of yogic practice showed statistically significant results (p-value < 0.001*). Respiratory endurance parameters (BHTi, BHTe, and 40mmHg) were also found to be statistically significant (p-value < 0.001*).

Conclusion: There was a significant increase in all the above parameters after the intervention of 8 weeks. Both ANB and Om chanting are yogic breathing forms that can also be used as complementary alternative medicine in people with chronic obstructive lung diseases along with drugs.

Keywords: ANB, Pranayam, BHTi, BHTe, 40mmHg, Pulmonary function.

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Introduction

Yogic breathing, also known as PRANAYAM, is the most ancient basis of yoga practice, which involves a conscious, controlled & regulated breathing exercise that has been said to produce observable physiological changes in an individual. [1]

The persistent conditioning of breathing patterns through the regular practice of Pranayama can lead to significant improvements in pulmonary function in healthy individuals. There are various forms of pranayama's, like, nostril breathing (double, single, or alternate), abdominal breathing, forceful breathing and vocalized (chanting) breathing, which are performed at varying rates and depths. [2]

Alternate nostril breathing (ANB) is considered one of the best forms of breathing exercises, as it promotes sympathovagal balance, which improves autonomic functions. Yogic breathing has been

shown to effectively decrease oxidative stress. Additionally, it has been found that it reduces the amount of free radicals and enhances the activity of superoxide dismutase (SOD) in healthy individuals. [3] Both ANB & OM chanting are yogic breathing forms that affect different body systems, especially the respiratory system. [4] OM is made of 3 syllables, A,U, and M, which exert their influence by means of vibrations. It is an important exhalation exercise to improve the pulmonary function. It is said to cure many illnesses. [3,5]

In order to see the effectiveness of these age-old breathing techniques on pulmonary functions, we examined volunteers with the help of a simple, non-invasive method of Pulmonary Function test - Spirometry. We were also curious to know the effect these yogic breathing exercises will have on the endurance of respiratory muscles. There are

many studies elaborating on the effect of these breathing exercises on the Autonomic function tests and, thus, their effect on reducing stress. The pattern of breathing may also directly strengthen the respiratory muscles, leading to increased respiratory endurance. Very few research scholars have focused their research purely on pulmonary functions and respiratory endurance.

Examining the demanding pace of modern life, where there's little time for physical activity, exposes our society to an increased risk of lifestyle-related illnesses. Incorporating these exercises into our daily routines can assist in adapting to today's hectic schedules, as these remarkable ancient breathing techniques remain largely untapped.

Materials and Methods

The study group consisted of a total of 150 healthy young adults within the age range of 18 to 25 years, who were recruited from staff and students in SGT Medical college, Gurgaon. The study was conducted in the Department of Physiology of SGT Medical College, Gurgaon. After getting approval from the Institutional Ethics committee, the subjects were recruited as per the inclusion and exclusion criteria as follows:

Inclusion Criteria: Both genders in the age group of 18 to 25 years were included.

Exclusion Criteria: Individuals having a habit of tobacco chewing, smoking, and consuming alcohol; a medical history of systemic disorders, particularly respiratory tract conditions; and any other allergy

conditions; medical history of consistent medication for any illness; subjects with chest and spine deformities like kyphosis and scoliosis; Pregnant, Post-partum or lactating females; subjects engaging in any pranayama/ yoga/ exercise/ meditation etc. before recruitment into the study were excluded.

After taking informed consent, anthropometric parameters like age, height and weight were recorded and the baseline data of the spirometry parameters like FEV₁; FEF_{25-75%} & for respiratory endurance – BHT_i, BHT_e, 40mmHg under research were collected before introducing the intervention.

Interventions: Subjects practiced the combination of Alternate nostril breathing and Om chanting before the lunch break around 12- 12:30 pm under the supervision for a duration of 10 minutes (5mins for each protocol as given below) for the period of 6 days/week for 8 weeks.

Om Chanting: Participants were instructed to get into the sukhasana posture and take a deep breath. They were then urged to exhale while producing the sound "OM" and continue doing so until they were unable to exhale any further.

For ANB: subjects were instructed to close the right nostril with their right thumb and bring right elbow to the level of right shoulder, inhale and exhale through left nostril first slowly and repeat the procedure through the other nostril

Flow of events

Figure 1: Flow of events

Breathe holding time (BHT)

When in the sitting position, the subjects were instructed to hold their breath. The patient was instructed to hold their breath until they could no longer do so voluntarily, and the duration was recorded using a timer. BHT was noted at the end of inspiration (BHT_i) and at the end of expiration (BHT_e).

Respiratory endurance test (40mm Hg test):

This test utilized a mercury sphygmomanometer. The rubber tubing connecting the mercury reservoir to the BP cuff was detached.

The participant was directed to inhale deeply and then close their nostrils, exhaling into the tube until the mercury reached a level of 40mm.

They were then advised to maintain this level for as long as they could. The time was recorded using a stopwatch.

Data analysis

The data was analyzed by statistical analysis of baseline and post intervention assessments of the total subjects (n = 149), by using students t- test. Pre and post assessment were analyzed using paired t-test. P < 0.05 was considered as significant.

Results

Table 1: Comparison of effect of 8 weeks of ANB & Om chanting

Variables	Before	After	P value
FEV ₁ (L/min)	2.64	3.03	<0.0001*
FEF ₂₅₋₇₅ % (L/min)	4.85	5.47	<0.0001*
BHT _i (sec)	34.37	45.43	<0.0001*
BHT _e (sec)	23.61	31.03	<0.0001*
40mmHg (sec)	25.47	34.71	<0.0001*

Figure 2: graphical comparison of effect of 8 weeks of ANB & Om chanting

The total of 164 subjects were recruited (Mean SD age, BMI) for the study, and complete assessment pre- and post-intervention was done for 149 subjects (15 subjects were lost for follow-up assessment). There was a significant increase in all the parameters observed including FEV₁, FEF_{25-75%}, BHT (inspiration & expiration) and 40mmHg test of respiratory endurance.

Discussion

The result of our study showed a significant increase in FEV₁, FEF_{25-75%}, BHT, and 40mmHg test of respiratory endurance. This significant improvement in FEV₁ is supported by many studies done in the past, as they have also seen beneficial effects on the pulmonary parameters.

The study done by Bamne S N, supports our study, and shows a significant increase in FEV₁, but this was done in elderly subjects, whereas our target population was healthy young adults. [6]

This visible improvement in FEV₁ can be due to the strengthening and development of the respiratory muscles after practicing breathing exercises and OM chanting. Due to its anxiolytic properties, ANB may alleviate emotional stress and mitigate the bronchoconstrictor effects. These respiratory exercises and OM chanting can be beneficial for individuals with obstructive pulmonary disorders, providing assistance to the affected people.

In our study, there is significant increase in FEF_{25-75%} as well, which is contradictory to the study done by Mooventhan A, Khode V. Here, when we look at the parameters, like in FEF_{25-75%}, the FEF_{75%} parameter individually showed no significant change, but the FEF_{25%} parameter showed significant increase.

Additionally, when we look at FEV₁, the same study supports our findings that there is a significant increase. [2]

Our study has also shown a significant increase in BHT. Similar research done by Shankarappa V. et al., have also shown significant improvement in lung parameters like FEV₁, FEF_{25-75%}, BHT, which supports the final outcome of our study. Another important aspect is that they also did the intervention in young population.

During the practice, there are prolonged periods of inspiration & expiration that cause maximum deflation of the lungs. As a result, the stretch receptors reduce the smooth muscle tone, which in turn leads to decreased airflow resistance & improved airway Caliber and this ultimately results in an increase in the FEF_{25-75%} and other dynamic lung parameters. [7] Similar results were also seen in previous studies which showed significant increase in the Breath Holding Time after the pranayama practice, and the improved respiratory efficiency of both central and peripheral chemoreceptors for hypercapnoea can be attributed to the practice of pranayama, which involves prolonged inspiration and expiration during training. [8]

This increase, as noted by Joshi et al., can be attributed to a reduced responsiveness to CO₂ in individuals practicing pranayamic breathing. A similar increase is observed in deep-sea and scuba divers who practice breath-holding. This is likely due to enhanced strength and endurance in their respiratory muscles, which delays fatigue and allows for extended breath-holding periods. [9]

Madanmohan et al. also supports our study with respect to the increase in breath holding time and the increase in 40mmHg test of respiratory endurance. This increase in breath holding time is seen more at the end of inspiration as compared to

expiration in our study as well as in the referenced study.

BHT is dependent on the initial lung volume, willpower, and strength of the respiratory muscles. Initial deep inhalation & larger lung volume may help increase the possibility of the breath holding for a longer period of time. Continuous yoga practice helps to get control over respiration by over-riding stimuli to respiratory centres which may be responsible for overall enhanced respiratory endurance. It can be concluded that breathing exercises can modify the sensitivity of chemoreceptors with increased respiratory endurance. [2,7]

This overall significant improvement in the respiratory endurance and pulmonary parameters could be due to reduced sympathetic activity after the practice of ANB and Om chanting. The bronchodilation with regular practice could have helped in improving the breathing patterns and decreasing the tone of muscles of respiration. This helps in better usage of the bronchioles and greater perfusion and helps to improve the pulmonary parameters and increase the respiratory endurance in healthy as well as affected population. [10]

Conclusion

To summarize, our study illustrates that regular practice of ANB & Om chanting can lead to significant improvement in respiratory parameters & it should be advised & added along with the drugs as complimentary alternative medicine in patients with obstructive lung diseases so as it help in today's busy lifestyle while investing very less time this can lead to give good results in healthy as well as affected population with obstructive lung disease

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